

Original article

The Role of Strategic Analysis (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threats) SWOT in Improvement of Performance at Benghazi Medical Center

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INTRODUCTION

In healthcare today, challenges surface almost daily in terms of finance, reform, government mandates and policy, technology, and customer satisfaction. It is crucial that healthcare leaders step back and continually assess the organization's strategic plan. In fact, strategic thinking, assessing and modeling are becoming requirements for an organization to survive the turbulent healthcare climate [1]. Organizational performance includes strategic planning, operations, financial, legal, and organizational development. Organization may achieve its goals when each of the employee understand their roles and responsibilities for the organization, and there should be continues communication between management, leader and employee to set performance expectations, monitor program and achieve a good result [2].

Strategic planning is an essential and important stage of the process administrative, as it represents a way of thinking and differentiating between methods and methods of work, to choose the best alternatives suitable for the available capabilities on the one hand, and the nature of the objectiveness desired to be achieved [3]. Organizations began to practice strategic planning because of its positive impact on their performance in a world characterized by rapid change and development in various walks of life, where many have been able to do so many organizations can achieve high

ABSTRACT

This study conducted to measure the role of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats Analysis "SWOT Analysis" in improving the performance at Benghazi Medical Centre. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among patients staying in the medical department in a BMC. Data collected it was revised, coded and fed to statistical software SPSS "Version 23". The study was based on a questionnaire that was distributed to 300 Libyan patients' participants in BMC (Department of Internal Medicine). The current study illustrated that 4.12 of the sample size agree with (the center's facilities are easily accessible,) and 3.93 of them agree with (lack of medication in the center's pharmacy staff.), while 3.57 of them didn't agree with (there are training opportunities for students and recent graduates.), and about 3.29 of the sample size neutral with (shortage of nursing staff.). The study suggests that the necessity of strengthening hospital management in providing the service correctly and for the first time. The necessity of providing a sufficient number of qualified nurses.

levels of success thanks to strategic planning, which Its strength lies in preparing, facing the future, solving problems, taking advantage of strengths, and Weaknesses, opportunities, threats, (SWOT) limiting, seizing, mitigating confronting developments and emergency situations ,this would improve the performance of organizations in a better way, develop their work and achieve their goals [4].

SWOT analysis is the most important method for diagnosing strengths and weaknesses in the organization's activities its various resources, available opportunities and threats it faces, which it uses to achieve its goals, mission and strategy, as well as potential, as it is an important and necessary analytical tool for every organization that enables management to determining the directions necessary to formulate appropriate strategies in light of the rapid and continuous economic changes in the environment, technological, social and civilized ones, as well as lead to working effectively and continuously to reduce the risks to which they may be exposed the organization. It is one of the most important factors that enable the organization to improve its performance, and lead to achieving competitive advantages [5]. Therefore, the current study was aimed to study the Role of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats Analysis “SWOT Analysis” in Improving the Performance at Benghazi Medical Center, and to determine the impact of SWOT Analysis Elements in improving the performance of Management Processes in the Benghazi medical center.

METHODS

Study design and setting

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted, during the period between Dec 2021 to Feb 2022 in Benghazi Medical Center, Benghazi, Libya. All patients who frequently visited the medical department in BMC were included. Data collected from patients was coded to protect identity and privacy and their consent was taken. A pilot study on a representative sample was conducted before starting the field work it was conducted to test the clarity of questionnaire and to identify obstacles and problems that may be detected.

Interviewing patient was conducted by using structured interview questionnaire adopted from the literature [6]. The questionnaire was included five sections. The first section was consisted of questions about socio-demographic data of patient "age, gender, education level." the period of staying in the BMC, causes of the inter to BMC, and number of entry times to the BMC. The second section includes 9 items to measuring the strengths of the BMC, while the third section had included 9 items to measuring the weaknesses of the BMC- Section four: includes also 9 items to expect the opportunities of the BMC. The fifth section includes another 9 items to estimate the volume of threats facing the BMC-

Statistical analysis

Data was presented as mean \pm SD and analyzed using SPSS version 23. Deviation was used to summarized the categorical variables. Reliability for all statement was examined by Cronbach’s Alpha in this study are .826 implies that the instrument is highly reliable.

RESULTS

The socio- demographic characteristics of the participants were described in Table 1. About 72.7% of the sample are females and 27.3% are males, and the highest percentage of their age is 31.3% (48_57 years). About 39.0% of the sample did not have an educational qualification, 40% of the sample stay in the center from (5 days or less), 68.7% indicated that they entered the center to receive treatment, and 59.7% indicated that they entered the center more than once.

Table 1. Socio- demographic characteristics of the participants

Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percent	
Age	18-27 years	15	5.0
	28-37 years	17	5.7
	38-47 years	53	17.7
	48-57 years	94	31.3
	58-67 years	82	27.3
	68 years and over	39	13.0
Gender	male	82	27.3
	female	218	72.7
Educational level	High school or less	95	31.7

	Diploma	50	16.7
	none	117	39.0
	Bachelor	35	11.7
	Master	3	1.0
The length of stay in the hospital	5days or less	120	40.0
	6-10 days	87	29.0
	11-15 days	75	25.0
	16-20 days	13	4.3
	21 days or more	5	1.7
Reason for admission to hospital	Having surgery	88	29.3
	Receiving treatment	206	68.7
	Other remember	6	2.0
The number of admissions to the same hospital until the present time	Once	121	40.3
	More than once	179	59.7

Table 2 illustrates that 4.12 of the sample size agree with (the center's facilities are easily accessible), about 3.64 of them agree with (the staff in the center are medical and administrative staff in a decent manner) and 3.45 of them agree with (the center shows a high interest in solving the problems that patients suffer from). About 3.11 from the was neutral with (the service is provided in the center correctly from the first time), 3.00 of them neutral (the service is provided at the center at the times promised), 3.51 agree to (the information received for patients is understandable and clear) and 3.68 agree to (the center keeps records of patients upon review). Also 2.82 of the sample size neutral (the center provides the service on time) and 2.64 of them neutral to (the center's employees provide services to patients quickly and do not delay in responding to their requests).

Table 2. Strengths in improving the performance at Benghazi Medical Centre

Strength's axis	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Level of agreement
The center's facilities are easily accessible.	300	4.1233	.88169	Agree
The staff in the center are medical and administrative staff in a decent manner	300	3.6433	1.14038	Agree
The center shows a high interest in solving the problems that patients suffer from	300	3.4533	1.04793	Agree
The service is provided in the center correctly from the first time	300	3.1100	1.28194	Neutral
The service is provided at the center at the times promised	300	3.0067	1.35378	Neutral
The information received for patients is understandable and clear	300	3.5167	1.11379	Agree
The center keeps records of patients upon review	300	3.6833	.73361	Agree
The center provides the service on time	300	2.8267	1.36486	Neutral
The center's employees provide services to patients quickly and do not delay in responding to their requests	300	2.6467	1.36186	Neutral
first general axis	300	3.3344	80931	Neutral

Table 3 illustrates that 2.66 of the sample size neutral with (waiting time for the purpose of examination and inspection is not acceptable.), 3.93 of them agree with (lack of medication in the center's pharmacy staff.) and 2.15 of them didn't agree with (the center does not respect patients' privacy). About 2.28 from them didn't agree with (the waiting place and the seating are inappropriate and uncomfortable), 1.96 of them didn't agree with (the distance between the residence and the center is not acceptable), 2,26 didn't agree to (the infrastructure of the center is dilapidated), and 2.65 neutral to (the lack of care of medical personnel to protect your safety (by sterilizing their hands, wearing gloves, etc.). Also 2.24 of the sample didn't agree (lack of respect for your visitors by staff and nurses.) and 2.81 of them neutral (lack of hygiene in the emergency department).

Table 3. Weakness in improving the performance at Benghazi Medical Centre

Weakness axis	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Level of agreement
Waiting time for the purpose of examination and inspection is not acceptable.	300	2.6633	1.36487	Neutral
Lack of medication in the center's pharmacy Staff	300	3.9333	1.21675	Agree
The center does not respect patients' privacy	300	2.1567	1.23445	I don't agree
The waiting place and the seating are inappropriate and uncomfortable	300	2.2833	1.34502	I don't agree
The distance between the residence and the center is not acceptable	300	1.9633	1.16899	I don't agree
The infrastructure of the center is dilapidated	300	2.2667	1.23314	I don't agree
The lack of care of medical personnel to protect your safety (by sterilizing their hands, wearing gloves, etc.)	300	2.6533	1.26959	Neutral
Lack of respect for your visitors by staff and nurses	300	2.2467	1.16778	I don't agree
Lack of hygiene in the emergency department	300	2.8167	1.08950	Neutral

Table 4 illustrates that 2.37 of the sample size didn't agree with (the center has highly qualified nursing staff.), about 3.57 of them didn't agree with (there are training opportunities for students and recent graduates.), 3.44 of them agree with (there is a suitable environment for patients in the field of providing medical services), and 2.94 from them neutral with (response of the center's management to patients when complaints are submitted to them). About 2.93 of them neutral with (a sufficient number of ambulances is available to serve patients) and that 2,01 didn't agree to (most of the medicines are available in the center's pharmacy).

Also 3.25 of the sample neutral (the high skill of the medical staff working in the center) and 2.93 of them neutral (the center provides services at all times and 24 hours a day) and 3.17 neutral to (the center's management communicates the results of laboratory tests to the patient).

Table 4. Opportunities in improving the performance at Benghazi Medical Centre

Opportunities axis	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Level of agreement
The center has highly qualified nursing staff.	300	2.3733	1.43089	I don't agree
There are training opportunities for students and recent graduates.	300	3.5767	.82039	I don't agree
There is a suitable environment for patients in the field of providing medical services.	300	3.4467	.87352	Agree
Response of the center's management to patients when complaints are submitted to them.	300	2.9467	.91649	Neutral
A sufficient number of ambulances is available to serve patients.	300	2.9367	.84164	Neutral
Most of the medicines are available in the center's pharmacy.	300	2.0100	1.09265	I don't agree
The high skill of the medical staff working in the center.	300	3.2500	1.19678	Neutral
The center provides services at all times and 24 hours a day.	300	2.9367	1.32104	Neutral
The center's management communicates the results of laboratory tests to the patient.	300	3.1767	1.09367	Neutral
third general axis	300	2.9615	.58921	Neutral

Table 5 illustrates that 3.29 of the sample size neutral with (shortage of nursing staff.), 3.01 of them neutral with (the number of beds does not accommodate the number of patients.), 3.19 of them neutral with (there is one specialist in the center.), 2.35 from them didn't agree with (lack of electric generators in the center), 3.32 of them neutral with (food quality and hygiene are not good), and that 2.82 neutral to (inability to provide medical devices, especially ventilators). Also 2.89 of the sample neutral (the center's inability to receive patients, especially in the field of intensive care rooms.),

2.46 of them didn't agree with (the treatment method by doctors and staff in the center is not good), and 2.49 didn't agree to (sterilization of medical devices and equipment is not good).

Table 5. Threats in improving the performance at Benghazi Medical Centre

Threats axis	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Level of agreement
Shortage of nursing staff.	300	3.2967	1.33213	Neutral
The number of beds does not accommodate the number of patients.	300	3.0167	.96583	Neutral
There is one specialist in the center.	300	3.1967	.94921	Neutral
Lack of electric generators in the center.	300	2.3533	1.02240	I don't agree
Food quality and hygiene are not good.	300	3.3267	1.29830	Neutral
Inability to provide medical devices, especially ventilators.	300	2.8200	1.04462	Neutral
The center's inability to receive patients, especially in the field of intensive care rooms.	300	2.8967	.96389	Neutral
The treatment method by doctors and staff in the center is not good.	300	2.4600	1.32195	I don't agree
Sterilization of medical devices and equipment is not good	300	2.4900	1.32505	I don't agree
forth general axis	300	2.8730	.65375	Neutral

DISCUSSION

The result of the present study revealed that approximately two thirds of the study subjects were females, most of them were in the age group ranged between (48-57) years, majority of the studied sample is stay in the hospital (5 days or less. This finding is similar to that of a study in Kuwait 2010 [6], which founded that health services depend on the quality of health care. and there is a statistically significant effect on the quality of health care for patient satisfaction. Most of study subjects had admission to hospital for receiving treatment, and the number of admissions to the same hospital until the present time is more than once. This is consistent with Turkish study conducted in 2014 [7] which founded that patient safety was the main concern and the purpose of ED and the vulned ability of the patients, they may be attributed to the fact patient satisfaction used in improvement of performance in health care.

The current study revealed that the strengths of the BMC have the highest mean score was center's facilities are easily accessible, and this is in line with study in South Korea [8] which founded that if policy makers of tourist destinations utilize the approach of this study (SWOT-AHP), they will be able to obtain more comprehensive decision-making tool for their effective strategic planning than using a traditional method (e.g., SWOT). This may be attributed to the fact that easily accessible is most important in the meeting of quality standards for health care facilities.

The present study revealed that the weaknesses of the Benghazi medical center have the highest mean score was lack of medication in the center's pharmacy staff, and this is similar to study in Sudan [9] which founded that the healthcare strategy enforcement, appropriate resource allocation changes and improved communication system in different level of the system components are the main pathways to accomplish the goals that needs to be achieved. It is also encouraged to further promote the use of health information system (HIS), improve quality of data, and emphasize on importance of dissemination of findings, providing medical personnel with incentives, providing fundamental infrastructures, and emphasis on community empowerment, disease prevention, and health promotion.

The current study revealed that the opportunities of the Benghazi medical center the highest mean score was there are training opportunities for students and recent graduates, and this is in consistent with study in United Kingdom and republic of Ireland in 2020 [10] which founded that the (SWOT) analysis and embedded pedagogical theory of these changes has been presented in the hope that anatomists feel more confident in their decision-making. It is hoped that the adaptations utilized by universities will ultimately translate to a lasting positive change in the delivery of anatomical education; and as such there are plans to assess the sustainability of these modalities with a follow-up survey, this may be attributed to the fact that the health care facilities are suitable environment for research and academic purposes.

The present study revealed that the threats of the BMC approximately highest mean score was food hygiene, this is in consistent with study in Serbia 2010 [11] which founded that one of the most frequently used methods in planning is SWOT analysis it is used to evaluate the organization and performance of the growing system. It offers a simple way to describe the environment, and the ultimate goal of strategic planning in which SWOT is an early stage is the development and adoption of a strategy that leads to good relationships between factors. It's a useful tool for identifying

needs and forecasting, service believes that the diet must be improved due to the patients, who are children's age, the success of the treatment, the quality of the food, the variety and the number of meals is inadequate, and this finding may be attributed to the fact that the food hygiene is a key factor in treatment protocols and prevention, and the analytical tool (SWOT ANALYSIS). If used in the early stages of the planning process, it can be helpful the managers of health care facilities in decision making and taking action to solve the problems that faces health care tasks and play key role in the health promotion.

CONCLUSION

Based on the patients' point of view, the highest average of the strengths was the ease of access to the location of the center, the highest average of the weaknesses of the center was the lack of medicines inside the pharmacy. The highest average of the opportunities was the presence of training opportunities for students and recent graduates, in terms of threats, the highest average was the quality of the food and hygiene are not good.

Ethical considerations

Data collected from patient was coded to protect identity and privacy and their consent was taken. The purpose of the study was explained for each participant, they were also measuring that all information gathered would be in confidential manner and used only for the purpose of the study.

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Conflict of interest

There were no financial, personal, or professional conflict of interest to declare.

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دور التحليل الاستراتيجي (القوة, الضعف, الفرص, التهديدات) في تحسين الأداء في مركز بنغازي الطبي

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المستخلص

أجريت هذه الدراسة لقياس دور تحليل نقاط القوة والضعف والفرص والتهديدات في تحسين الأداء بمركز بنغازي الطبي, تم إجراء دراسة وصفية مقطعية بين المرضى المقيمين في قسم الطب في مركز بنغازي الطبي وتمت مراجعة البيانات التي تم الإصدار 23. اعتمدت الدراسة على استبيان تم توزيعه على SPSS300 جمعها وترميزها وتغذيتها بالبرنامج الإحصائي مريض ليبي مشارك في مركز بنغازي الطبي (قسم الطب الباطني). وكشفت الدراسة الحالية أن قوة مركز بنغازي الطبي البالغة 4.12% لديها أعلى متوسط درجات حيث يمكن الوصول إلى مرافق المركز بسهولة, ونسبة 2.66 نقاط الضعف في مركز بنغازي الطبي كان نقص الادوية لدي موظفي الصيدلانية في مركز بنغازي الطبي. وكان أعلى متوسط 2.37% هناك فرص تدريب للطلاب والخريجين الجدد. وكان 3.29% اعلي متوسط للتهديدات وتتمثل في النظافة والغذاء. وتشير الدراسة إلى ضرورة تعزيز إدارة المستشفى في تقديم الخدمة بشكل صحيح ولأول مرة ضرورة توفير العدد الكافي من الممرضين المؤهلين.

الكلمات الدالة: التحليل الاستراتيجي , تحسين الاداء, مركز بنغازي الطبي.